

Lived Experiences of Bachelor of Arts in English Language Interns in the Conduct of Flexible Learning Amid Pandemic

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Abstract

With the onset of pandemic and the degrading landscape of educational reforms as it lacks concrete measures to combat and establish sustainability in the context of the academe, educators are forced to embrace flexible learning against the backdrop of COVID-19 menace. This has brought a plethora of challenges both to the students and the scholars. This situation greatly affects the paradigm by which students were supposed to expose a scenario where they can experience the so-called meaningful experience. In this paper, it boils down to extracting and exploring on the lived experiences of the BAEL students who are teaching English- related subjects via flexible learning modality. The researcher randomly selected 7 participants for the study and they data were gathered through structured interview guide and the actual interview session to disambiguate gray areas as regards their responses. With the use of Colaizzi's model of phenomenological study, themes were surfaced with respect to their lived experiences- these entail student interns' technological challenge as they were having a hard time coping with the demands of technology especially with the use of various online platforms. Recommendations are given such as to expose student interns to more pedagogies and strategies so they can effectively articulate the lessons to the students. Similarly, they need technical expertise with regard to the use of educational platforms for easy facilitation of the lesson.

Keywords: Flexible Learning, student interns, pandemic, lived experiences, technological challenges

Introduction

The impact that covid-19 pandemic brings to society makes significant changes in diverse facets and industries. More importantly, lockdowns pave way for academic institutions to restrict their students to visit campuses for a traditional class, yet they are given options to enroll themselves to modular learning modality to perpetuate learning amidst the debacles brought by pandemic 19 episode. In the study conducted by Adnan & Anwar (2020) as regards distance learning amid pandemic, students in Pakistan are found that they are having a hard time coping with their studies and it highlighted that "online learning cannot produce desired results in underdeveloped countries like Pakistan," one factor is the connectivity issue where students can't afford technical aspect of education.

With the restriction of face to face classes, students are limited to visit on sit, thereby relying to the instructions given by the professors in diverse educational and digital platforms, hence flexible learning modality. However, this educational trend sees a silver lining as it gives positive outcome to the new normal paradigm. According to Talosa & Dirain (2021) flexible learning modality purports innovation as it describes "learning opportunities and influencing factors on the self-efficacy of students."

Recent study by Kemp and Grieve (2014) suggested that students learn more in in-person classes due to the high demand of technological sophistications that students fail to cope with. Moreover, their study experiments two sets of students who were given activities- one in person modality, another in online learning. It goes on to say that activities are successfully complied with in face-to-face modality rather than online.

Similarly, there is direct correlation between the effect of pandemic to scholastic performance of the students amid lockdowns and isolation. In a study conducted Chisadza et al (2021), it attempts to juxtapose the reality of Covid-19 crisis and the impact it brings to the students. Despite the fact that learning is made easy because of technology and online resources, the study shows that there was "lower academic performance for students who found transitioning to online setting."

These are just some of the realities that learners face in this flexible leaning modality. But there is underrated reality that a group of students face- these are interns, 'practicumers', interns who are graduands and are expected to cross the stage to receive their hard-earned diploma at the end of the school year. In a published article, it posits that a college student needs to comply all academic requirements before he/she can apply for graduation in any program he/she is enrolled to. Internship, according to Merriam- Webster dictionary, refers "to the phase of training covered during such service." This becomes crucial requirements for any student who wants to earn his/ her Bachelor's degree. However, this becomes a struggle for them as their experience is not conventional- they are to adhere to flexible learning modality.

In a study piloted by Iradel & Cadosales (2021), it is posited that struggles are all evident when interns conduct classes via synchronous session. This is kind of challenge university students are also facing amid pandemic. Moreover, the study reveals that they had expectation that were not met, and they have challenges as regards the

delivery of the lesson distantly. However, positive light shows that they had "Acknowledged the presence of a solid support system and maintained a strong cognitive-social-teaching presence."

Similar study includes that of Valdez & Edjan (2021) which delves on the experiences of teaching internship in the country during pandemic episode. It is found out that despite the menace that Covid-19 brings to the people, "this has opened opportunities for greater involvement for pre-service teachers as they can be empowered to help in the teaching and learning process in the online environment."

However, the focus of this study boils down to the Bachelor of Arts in English Language students of Eastern Visayas State University. BAEL in the Philippines is a program which focuses on honing linguistic competence and literary dexterity of students. According to courses.com, AB English is a "four-year degree program that will teach one about structure, development, theories, and applications of languages." Moreover, this program focuses on delving upon language structure, establishing grammaticality, and adhering to appropriate language paradigm in diverse contexts. The challenge, therefore, is the establishment of rapport and foundation of communicative context where language classroom needs both verbal and non-verbal communication to elicit holistic language instruction.

Another study as regards the challenge of that intern students face is the level of readiness. This becomes indispensable tool to propel teachers toward embracing the profession they are committed to execute. The findings of the study of Ardiyansah (2021) show purport that the perceived readiness of pre-service teachers was considered an essential aspect in the teaching-learning process." The present study holds to this notion that internship establishes the springboard for a meaningful real profession that they are to embark in the future.

However, fewer studies are conducted with regard to the acclimatization of BAEL experiences in their online learning with the students. This attempts to fill the gap and establish paucity form other studies.

Moreover, this focuses on the lived experiences of the BAEL interns in their conduct of flexible learning, there is teacher facilitation, or a supervising teacher educator who guides interns in teaching to the students.

Lived experiences entail the qualitative and substantial experiences of the respondents with respect to the exposure, problems, and their daily encounter with phenomena. Similarly, lived experience pertains to "representation and understanding of a researcher or research subject's human experiences, choices, and options." This involves the social reality of the respondents, herein BAEL interns, who have exposure to teach under flexible learning modality.

According to the memorandum in relation to the Student Practicum guidelines of Languages and Literature Department, Student interns need 300 hours for their internship, and this will expose to them to the reality of a teaching profession. This is the right avenue for the researcher, therefore, to investigate in the experiences, challenges and coping mechanism of these interns as they practice their would-be profession in the unprecedented effect of Covid -19 fiasco.

Statement of the problem

Envisioned to find solutions to problems in online teaching system, this study explores on the following research questions. This will anchor the interpretation, analysis, and discussion of the study.

1. What are the challenges faced by Bachelor of Arts in English Language 4th year interns in the conduct of online learning modality?
2. What are the experiences of BAEL interns in teaching both language and literature in class?
3. What implications can we infer from the experiences of the BAEL interns?

Significance of the study

This study will be help to the college department and offices to help facilitate the learning experiences of the BAEL interns in their conduct of online learning classes. specifically, following will stakeholders will benefit from this study:

School administrators because with the experiences of these interns, this could be an avenue to establish concrete and tangible policy making and guidelines to ascertain learning experience of the students with safety.

To the Cooperating teachers who work with the student interns side by side as they give instructions to the interns. They can provide meaningful inputs to the interns so that they can deliver a quality education anchored on the university's mission and vision.

To the Future researchers who can peruse this thesis and attempt to fill the gap by inviting a larger number of respondents for a more comprehensive lived experiences study.

Scope and Delimitation of the study

This study is limited to the respondents, who are fourth year students of Eastern Visayas State University under Languages and Literature Department of the College of Arts and Sciences. Specifically, these are Bachelor of Arts in English Language Interns who help professors facilitate synchronous discussion in the classes they are similarly handling.

Review of Related Literature

Several studies have been conducted with regard to the flexible learning and the challenges teachers encounter in the context of pandemic paradigm.

In a research conducted by Pepito (2022), there are a number of intern students who are exposed to teaching young learners under the new normal setting. The experienced could have been enriched had they taught in person set up. However, with the government's imposition of strict Covid- 19 protocols, these teachers are forced to have their internship online. The result of the study shows that there was a level of unpreparedness on the teachers' training since they were not exposed to teaching online, especially with the utilization of the online/ digital platforms. The study goes on to say that even the Supervising Teacher- Educators don't have the repertoire of digital knowledge which they could have cascaded the information to their student intern. This study manifests the drawback of online learning and the less meaningful experience of the interns in the classroom instruction.

Similarly, a study conducted by Triyason et al (2020) posits the effort of the universities to adopt to the new normal paradigm which is caused by the Covid- 19 problem. There is a so called hybrid room to "allow online and physical attendees interaction during the operating sessions." Moreover, students are given freedom to choose modality which is more convenient to them amid flexible learning. Needless to say, the paper describes the problems and obstacles that arise during the implementation of prototype rooms. This includes crowd control of the learners who are scheduled to report on site, mismanagement, among others. but Triyason (2020) suggests solutions to achieve organized and more substantiated hybrid classroom instruction.

As the study focuses on the English Language interns, a related study conducted by Kissau (2015) is cited. The researcher invites Language Teacher candidates in relation to their experiences in both Flexible learning and face-to-face instruction. It goes on to say that the tutelage of the cooperating teachers plays an integral role in shaping significant experiences of the Language interns in the classroom. Additionally, the prior experiences of these interns in their exposure to teaching students are key indicators of exemplifying and integrating their instructional practices.

Furthermore, an Australian-based research conducted by Brant & Crowther (2020) recounts the boon and the bane of flexible working system among its workers. With the country being affected by the Covid-19, industries initiated a shift from office work to remote work. A number of participants are invited for the study, and common themes emerge in relation to the advantages and disadvantages of flexible learning modality. Consequently, it shows that it becomes beneficial for the students especially those who have lesser retention in short term. The lesser the number of classes are, the more effective the learning is since the substance of the discussion is underscored. However, the drawback of reporting to office work suggests that it is "difficult for many students who are unable to attend workplaces to complete required hours due to other range of other work, study, and life factors." With the multifaceted roles of interns, their function does not only limit to the instruction per say, but with the preparation, consultation, and even personal appointment they are to manage. In this regard remote work gives them opportunity to be flexible and offers them convenient time to do work in a more efficient manner.

The current study focuses on the college students, also called here as Teacher interns who do their internship online through the application of diverse digital platforms. It becomes convenient for some, but other students prefer the traditional way of exposing themselves to pre-service teaching experience. As a matter of fact, the study conducted by Hermida (2020) juxtaposes the experiences of College students and their preferences to learn amid pandemic. Admittedly, study shows an indispensable role of technology in surviving online classes, but the college students preferred face-to-face learning over online learning. This is because of the limited resources, interaction, and input the students establish via flexible learning. In-person instruction gives more time to students to ask the professors as regards complexity in the topic being discussed considering the proximity of the more knowledgeable others (MKO) who can help them enlighten what the topic is.

Meanwhile, a study conducted by Rizun & Strzelecki (2020) deviates from the perspective of the former study. In the context of Polish college and graduate students, the researcher attempts to explore on the acceptability of flexible learning adherence among the participants. The study further arrives at the conclusion that students have positive acceptability and appropriate attitude towards "distance learning." In addition to that, major themes emerge such as enjoyment, self-efficacy, and usefulness in relation to the conduct of remote classes. this offers opportunities for teachers to maximize the use of online learning in such a way that students' motivation will remain despite the complexity pandemic situation brings.

Locally, studies have been conducted in relation to the magnitude of pandemic in new normal paradigm. In the flexible learning system, a number of respondents are interviewed as regards the challenges and their coping mechanism in the context of continuing learning. It is found that the study of Barrot et al (2021) infers some of the challenges teacher intends face in the conduct of the instruction. Moreover, one challenge was “linked to their learning environment at home, and the least challenge was the technological literacy and competency.”

A related study of Comas- Quinn (2011) assesses the effect of the integration of flexible learning in a distance language course the teacher provides. It is found out that technological challenges are problems which are faced by the teachers in online learning, but more so, there was negative attitude of the teachers about the course they are teaching. It is proposed then that teachers should strengthen their pedagogic skills as regards the content they are handling combined with advance trainings and webinars about using digital educational platforms.

The present study, meanwhile, boils down to the challenges of Graduating English Language Interns in their conduct of instruction and preparation of materials for the flexible learning. More specifically, this focuses on the pedagogic integration and the mastery of the content the students imbibe in their internship experience.

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

This study will utilize Colaizzi’s framework of analyzing the data. As a qualitative paper, this highlights experiences, social realities, and challenges of the respondents with regard to their exposure to flexible learning. Through the series of interviews and guide questions administration, research questions will be answered via the paradigm of Colaizzi’s. below is the diagram through which the analysis will be gathered.

Figure (1) illustrates the process of descriptive phenomenological data analysis created by Colaizzi (1978).

Figure 1. A summary of Colaizzi’s strategy for phenomenological data analysis. (developed by the author in 1/9/2010).

Figure 1 Colaizzi’s framework of analyzing the data

Methodology

Research Design

This study adheres to descriptive phenomenological method. The main objective is to disambiguate issues through the conduct of empirical study and interviews to the respondents to give light to the issues that are faced in the context of flexible learning. Furthermore, Giorgi (1997) recounts that using this approach will “make clear and

understand the most essential meaning of a phenomenon of interest from the perspective of those directly involved in it. It describes the experiences of the BAEL students, who are currently enrolled in their internship course, and are assigned to teach online depending upon the Faculty members they are assigned to. It identifies not only some of the challenges and criticisms with regard to their internship experiences but also it strengthens pedagogic and curricular underpinnings using a scientific approach to phenomenological research.

The participants of the study are comprised of fourth year Bachelor of Arts in English Language, herein called interns. They are currently enrolled at the same university, school year 2021-2022, second semester. These are comprised of 7 participants who are chosen randomly.

Research Instrument

The instrument used was a researcher made questionnaire checklist to gather the needed data for the students' profile, the draft of the questionnaire was drawn out based on the researcher's readings, scrutiny of related studies, academic literature, and researches relevant to the present study. Questions are attuned based on the core components stipulated in the statement of the problem to elicit commendable reasons and germane data from the respondents. Furthermore, the researcher will interview the respondents to saturate pertinent data required of the paper.

Validation of Instrument

The researcher crafted relevant questions that will answer research questions in the form of interview guide. These have been reviewed to establish the validity of such instrument. Moreover, these questionnaires will be subject for verification from a professor in college who is erudite in the field of qualitative research. It will be finalized and will be given to the respondents for the interview administration.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher crafts a letter to the head of the eastern languages and literature department, asking the latter that the researcher be allowed to conduct study to the select BAEL interns who are currently enrolled in internship program. The researcher then will create a google form with an interview guide questions where they can answer the said guide questions. Afterwards, he will ask for a considerable time to have one-on-one interview with the respondents. After the data collection, such will be subject to analysis and interpretation and the data will be treated with utmost substance and primary importance.

Figure 3 Schematic diagram of the process of data analysis

Analysis of Data

Upon collection of the data from the respondents, the qualitative research format commences by categorizing major themes from the responses. These will be manually investigated and this will be sorted out to surface the recurring themes that the respondents answered. From those themes, this will be further compacted to related themes until such will be different from another. The themes are all over the place. Color coding will be applied to avoid confusion, theme 1 will be labeled one color, theme 2 will be labeled another, etc. at the end of the coding, everything will be collected and will be put in proper places. Diverse coding methods will be utilized then: pattern coding to examine initial codes, patterns, trends and relationships; then the focused coding, to identify the most frequent or significant initial codes; then the axial coding to identify the core category

Ethical Consideration

The data to be gathered will be treated with utmost confidentiality. The interview session will be done online, and the respondents will be presented data privacy act before the conduct of the actual interview. They will have electronic signature for consent that interviewed will be conducted online and this will be recorded. After the treatment of the data, the recording will be deleted to maintain the anonymity of the students. The name will be optional and it will be made sure that their identity is highly protected.

Results and Discussion

Data Analysis

This section deals with the analysis, findings, and discussion of the study conducted. The researcher randomly chooses 6 participants who are graduating students. The latter are currently enrolled in BAEL Practicum.

The analysis will be exemplified using a table below with the participants and their extracts of responses from the interview. From such, the researcher will be distinguishing the codes, categories, and themes which are all anchored from the interview and interpellation

Participant	Questions	Extracts	Codes/ Categories	Themes
P1	<p>Challenges:</p> <p>Experience</p> <p>Pedagogies:</p>	<p>--To have an internship in this time of pandemic is both negative and positive. Positive in a sense that I was able to experience to be in the field of teaching amid the current situation. However, what makes it negative is that I feel like I don't actually give my full potential in teaching unlike if it's in face to face.</p> <p>-- Well, for me, I can see that some students are eager to learn despite of the situation but there are students who are not really into learning. When I conduct synchronous classes, some students are participative while others, maybe, are just present for the sake of attendance.</p> <p>--- At first, I was nervous since the subject assigned to me was my subject when I was in first year and I already forgot about it. Nevertheless, I was able to teach the topics with the help of our CT.</p>	<p>Having internship via face-to-face could have been more meaningful. He could have done things which are interactive and substantial in in-person learning experience</p> <p>-different kinds of students flock together in synchronous session. Some students attend classes for content, some for attendance, and some for exposure</p> <p>- first time exposure to actual learning experience has been a memorable experience. He was both nervous and excited</p>	<p>The advantage of teaching face-to-face teaching modality.</p> <p>Diversity of students need various online activities to elicit meaningful learning process.</p> <p>Non-readiness of the interns as evident through some indicators: nervousness, stress, communicative barrier</p>
P2	Challenges:	-- Technological challenge sometimes, I experienced poor reception of signal and not so well-functioning laptop.	The participant delineated three challenges during synchronous session-	Unavailability of resources due to financial constraints

	<p>Experiences:</p> <p>Pedagogies:</p>	<p>Communicative challenge Socio-economic challenge there are times that I am unable to attend synchronous session as I'm having difficulty sometimes in purchasing mobile data.</p> <p>-- So far, I have no problem in interacting with the students. They are responsive and asked questions when experience equivocality regarding the topic, that made the virtual classroom setting interactive and engaging.</p> <p>-- Communication. My ability to deliver the topics in a comprehensive manner.</p>	<p>technological challenge Interaction challenge with the students and unavailability of resources when conducting classes. -the students are responsive and he really felt that it is literature class because they can freely express what they have in mind. -the participant has the command of the language, making it a lot easier for him to articulate the assigned topic in class</p>	<p>Proper teaching pedagogies may elicit more engaging and vibrant classroom discussion.</p> <p>Mastery of the topic should be considered. Articulation is one of the keys to grab the attention of the students</p>
<p>P3</p>	<p>Challenges:</p> <p>Experience</p> <p>Pedagogies:</p>	<p>As part of poorest of the poor family here in the Philippines the conducting of flexible learning gave so much impact to me and hardship since my family cannot afford buying a material for this platform. The challenges that I have encountered in flexible learning in terms of technological is that having a laptop that I can use in making my lessons and activities, it is really hard making our activities in a phone since it is only have s small screen so it gives me hard time making my requirements.</p> <p>--At first, I had a bit of a hard time to make a tasks and worksheet for my students, but through the guides or guidance of my cooperating teacher I've got a knowledge on how can I creating and preparing my tasks and worksheets for my students.</p> <p>-- Honestly, at first I feel nervous since it's new to me, but I don't have any choice but to follow those, but I overcome it through my determination by doing some reviews, enhancing myself from making learning materials and lastly, practicing myself in presenting my lesson.</p>	<p>The participant is having problems with smartphones and gadgets to use. It could have been better if he uses laptop for easy visibility since smartphones have small screens to facilitate class substantially.</p> <p>It's even more meaningful since the Cooperating teacher works side by side with them. She gives suggestions as to what to do, and how to attack the lesson in such a way that it becomes more engaging.</p> <p>-It goes with the level of preparation before the actual lesson eventuates. As a teacher, we must be well-verse with the content we are sharing to the students. Higher learning order thinking skills must</p>	<p>Technological problem arises with the lack of smartphones and unavailability of resources, thus they cannot buy load to join classes.</p> <p>With the tutelage of the cooperating teachers, the intern learns a lot as regard lesson delivery, approaches, and the like.</p> <p>Preparing for the lesson and creating higher order thinking skills question can substantiate the discussion students can get to think deeply and comprehensively</p>

			be integrated in the teaching learning process.	
P4	<p>Challenges:</p> <p>My experiences during flexible learning as an intern student, teaching language and literature is hard especially if it is conducted in online course. One of the most frequent challenges is communicative challenges during classes in flexible learning we cannot deny the fact that communication between student and teacher is limited due to the environment factor where classes conducted. Second the technological challenges in this type of learning modality internet connectivity is highly significant at all if the student or the teacher couldn't have enough or sufficient internet connection it might lead a substantial impart of knowledge as well as interaction which is important in learning.</p> <p>-- For my experiences teaching flexible learning is not worthwhile because I believe during flexible learning, I could not give my best efforts. Since, it is online theirs many factors affecting my performance just like technological challenges and communicative challenges.</p> <p>Experience</p>	<p>--My impression with regards to the topic presented in the syllabus for flexible learning actually this new learning system is pretty easy in comparison with the traditional face to face classes. Because it is very easy for student to cheat and copy paste the answers</p> <p>Pedagogies:</p>	<p>Communication becomes the hindrance towards achieving the appropriate learning objectives in class. The students cannot get the lesson right then and there it takes time. They need to repeat or paraphrase the question to elicit smooth response from the students.</p> <p>It is demotivating since they could not exemplify their skills to the utmost. It seems that flexible learning may not be enough to achieve meaningful internship experiences</p> <p>With the learning materials all available to the students via online platform, it would be easier for the students to get tempted to own plagiarized work</p>	<p>Students may be aloof to respond to the question, or it may be internet connectivity problem that made them unresponsive in class.</p> <p>Nothing can replace the quality education face-to-face modality offers. Flexible learning seems to produce half-baked learning.</p> <p>Plagiarized outputs make it easier for students to cheat and copy responses from eh internet especially during assessment</p>
P5	<p>Challenges:</p> <p>From what I have encountered during the internship program regarding sa technological challenges, sometimes I run into poor connectivity when it is raining. Thus, it becomes a barrier when it is to connecting with the class. Also, I have difficulties when I am not using my laptop because I can't see who among the students are participating.</p> <p>-- It is great and fulfilling because I have feedback from the learners through the given task. And I have also seen a different kind of view of the learners through the given task.</p> <p>Experience</p>		<p>Digital difficulty is evident. Poor connectivity makes the participant a lot stressful especially during the conduct of flexible learning.</p> <p>The participant gets to appreciate diversity in the flexible learning</p>	<p>Lack of computer and gadget to participate in the synchronous session.</p> <p>Feed backing is the key to confirm if the student gets to</p>

	Pedagogies:	-- The interactive instruction, wherein we facilitate the class and let them discuss the topic that was given to them. Then in the last part, we ask a question to the reporter as well as the class so that we will have an interactive discussion.	modality. Giving feedback can be on away to validate learning, and it will confirm if the idea sets the demands as to what is asked from the content. --the classroom is engaging since the presentation is per group. It becomes student-centered approach and the teacher is just there to facilitate the discussion. He clarifies, adds, and asks questions as regards the report presented. He also includes the whole class in answering general questions especially those that entail social issues in literature	be updated with the discussion considering the fact that the video and microphones are off during the conduct of synchronous session. Organized topic assignment can make the class more organized. The student will have sense of responsibility to do their task beforehand.
P6	Challenges:	I am a working student and I help my family with the expenses. However, with the onset of flexible learning, I need to allocate sufficient budget to buy mobile data in order to attend to a synchronous session. This is part of my mandate as student intern	Financial resource us a challenge as a working student. He gets to allocate budget for mobile data and smart phone maintenance.	Problems with finance becomes the utmost concern of the participant.
	Experience	-- Despite the nontraditional learning modality, I can still cope with the demands of flexible learning with the help of my co teachers. I can solicit ideas from them, and students get active when they are asked about questions which they could relate on.	Mostly, he has positive experience from the teaching internship. Students were mature enough to chew the morals stipulated and manifested in literary pieces.	The internship is meaningful knowing the fact that student gets to participate in the interpretation and throwing of insights from the piece discussed.
	Pedagogies:	-- As an English major, I could strategically communicate and frame questions in such a way that it become more interactive to elicit teaching-learning process.	The facility of the language is very important as teacher. It may not be perfect but at least he has the command of the language.	Different approaches may be implemented. Teacher should be model of language learning.

Findings and Discussion

Based from the analysis through coding and extracting of themes from interview and observation, answers from the research questions were surfaced. Challenges include lack of gadgets that hinders them to attend to synchronous

session. If there is even one, they have a hard time allocating budget for mobile data because of much consumption it eats up through synchronous session.

With regard to their experiences, it is motivating to teach when students recite and become more interactive in class. Some students are unresponsive and teacher interns need to do something to elicit response from class. It may be through paraphrasing, encouraging students through positive reinforcement, or relating the question to their situation to establish rapport.

Pedagogies may be a part of their lived experiences. They need to integrate appropriate method to establish vibrant class discussion. They also need to craft appropriate learning outputs that are based on the set learning outcomes from the syllabus. Lastly, they can employ preponderance of strategies to make the Language and Literature discussion more evocative.

Summary of Findings, Conclusion, and Recommendations

Summary

The teacher interns evidently experience challenges from their flexible learning teaching. During the pandemic, they were tasked to teach online alongside the cooperating teachers in the Language Unit.

Technological challenge:

The student interns do not have the capacity to cope with the demands of flexible learning. It is not because they are not technology-savvy, rather they don't have available resources to interact with such. For example, a participant doesn't have computer to use, instead, he uses smartphone to conduct and join classes. However, problem arises when he needs to present something like video clip and power point presentation to substantiate the discussion.

From what I have encountered during the internship program regarding sa technological challenges, sometimes I run into poor connectivity when it is raining. Thus, it becomes a barrier when it is to connecting with the class. Also, I have difficulties when I am not using my laptop because I can't see who among the students are participating.- Participant 1

While other participant is adept at utilizing online educational platform like Edmodo, moodle, or google classroom. He needs more training to master these helpful tools to teachers. He says: *"I am not adept at using online educational platforms and t really is struggle to me to cope with the demands of the flexible learning."* -Participant 5

Communicative challenge:

The participants generally have the mastery of the English Language. They can facilitate the discussion well with less supervision. However, teaching learning process does not only entail teacher education. gone are those days when teachers are the sage on the stage, rather, they give opportunities to students to be expressive especially in literature classes.

We all known that mostly places here in the Philippines has difficulties of internet or data connection, so it is really hard most of the time communicating through online platform our students or even our teachers. And this is the reason why mostly of our students and even me sometimes cannot joint or attend in our online class -Participant 3

Socio-economic challenge:

Alongside the pandemic that brought the country's economy to the lowest level. Typical Filipino families also suffer. As a result, there is unemployment, poverty, and economic recession. For student interns some of them engage on part time work to sustain their daily needs. This includes buying load for data allocation in order to attend to online classes or purchase smartphones to work on academic requirements. Data allocation seems to be a major problems online classes using google meet eats up much of the data, hence the load can easily expire

There are times that I am unable to attend synchronous session as I'm having difficulty sometimes in purchasing mobile data. -Participant 2

Experiences

The primary purpose of the student internship is to convert the theories the students have grasped into more pragmatic aspects of life. Internship plays an integral role to test and validate their skills if they really learned something to the program which they have majored in.

Based on the participants' responses, both negative and positive experiences have surfaced from their internship program. The internship lasted for a semester. There were able to accomplish things which the Professors or Cooperating Teachers were doing. They record attendance, they facilitate discussion, they call students to recite, they motivate students to continue learning amidst pandemic, and they inspire learners through the gems impressed in literary pieces.

Debauch arises when the intern seems not to deliver the lesson because of poor connectivity, yet flexibility is the key towards surpassing the challenges brought by pandemic

Despite problems that I encountered, specifically, in terms of signal reception, I am still able to comprehensively discuss the topics. -Participant 2

Similarly, the Teacher Interns become motivated when they see that students are interacting and sharing ideas about the lesson. Literature connects people and with the appropriate strategies in teaching literature, the student can freely express himself in the task that is assigned of him to accomplish. For instance, they are asked to present in class a spoken poetry. They were asked to craft the piece and present those in class. That becomes more engaging especially they share common themes about love, depression, and pandemic-related poems. Lastly, it may be disappointing because students fail to respond to what the teacher asks of him, yet consideration is a virtue that needs to be appreciated.

It is a struggle considering that flexible learning modality is non-traditional education. when I ask random questions about the topic, some tend to leave the group perhaps because the net is wobbling, or they may have technology-phobia where they may be afraid to speak out online. In this case, the teacher needs to paraphrase or repeat the question. It may also be on the part of the teacher's connectivity. It takes time confirming if the video, audio works. -Participant 6

Pedagogies

In teaching, it needs approaches, strategies and methods to be integrated. It becomes more challenging since the teacher interns have lesser professional subjects which could inform them of instruction, pedagogies, and strategies in teaching Language and Literature.

A teacher must be advance with regard to their knowledge in th discussion. He needs to study and becomes innovative as regards employing diverse strategies that could cater the needs of the learners. with this, he will effectively communicate and discuss the lesson more meaningfully to the students.

I need to be a researcher it is a must in flexible learning and patience, so I can communicate well with the learners. Asking a question to find out if they have prior knowledge of the topic, give them advanced learning material that they will know what to do next meeting. -Participant 3

Moreover, readiness in the in the conduct of the classes must be considered. Teachers need to plan the lesson at par with the learning objectives he has set. It may be a disadvantage still during the flexible learning set up because they students are prone to copy ideas from the internet which will negatively affect their learning. This is the reason why they can get low remark from the teacher.

Additionally, some students don't have time to read the instructions comprehensively. this may be part of pedagogy but since not everything can be explained synchronously, the teacher gives instruction through diverse online platforms, yet the students fail to read instructions before answering worksheets.

Some students don't follow instructions. I suppose they get lazy in reading comprehensive instructions in such a way that they tend to answer the questions without regard to the directions. As a result, they get a wrong output. Learning tasks are helpful as it confirms the learning process of the students. Some students submit those late due to a considerable reason. -Participant 6

Implications

The study gives a substantially meaningful output as regards the situation and lived experiences of the BAEL students and their engagement on Flexible learning. Concerns like unpreparedness may be considered by the Teacher interns. They must consider that they become role models inside the classroom, whatever they teach, students may apply such. Their teaching experience speaks of the plight they have from technological challenge to pedagogical challenges.

The desire to improve their teaching experience skills speak of the opportunities to advance their subskills through different life skills that could better their performance inside the classroom. They may attend trainings and seminar

to be more adept at using digital platforms as one faces flexible learning paradigm under COVID-19 Pandemic episode.

Conclusion

The lived experiences of the BAEL teaching interns are test of their readiness towards traversing the real sense of the world. as confirmed by previous studies, flexible learning lacks practical experience and interaction, and this becomes a hindrance to promote better and more engaging discussion with the students. The challenges that they face are common and salient features of pandemic- related concerns. Because of financial constraints, the interns cannot make update in their smartphones nor buy a laptop to perform better during synchronous session.

With regard to their experiences, they have to deal with students of diverse backgrounds, intelligence, and interests. Some students have solid interest with the course as evident with their punctual submission of the online learning worksheets. On the other hand, some questions of the students to the interns are not satisfied. The role of the Cooperating teachers come into place. He supports and backs up the discussion if the Teacher interns lack substance with regard to the concern of the students.

Teaching Language and Literature requires a repertoire of strategies to extensively deliver the lesson. They need more exposure and advance training to become proficient in the field of expertise.

Recommendation

Further research may be initiated with a larger group of participants to saturate data. Future researchers may likewise focus on the coping mechanism of the interns in relation to their lived experiences.

To the faculty members, this will be an opportune time to guide the Teacher interns as they become part of the teaching profession circle in the near future. They play indispensable role in giving their tutelage to the interns especially with the delivery of the lesson assessment, among others.

To the administrators, this may be an opportunity to expose students to more webinars that could help Teacher interns become adept at skills that are required in the field. These may include training in Google technology, Learning Management System, and Assessment processes to fairly give students what they deserve.

To Curricularists, this may give them realization to revisit the curriculum checklist and modify and add subjects which are relevant towards honing Teacher interns by offering them programs like curriculum development and Strategies and Methods in Teaching Language and Literature courses.

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